

Agrarian Relations during British Rule in South India

A Study

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ABSTRACT

From the earliest days, agriculture has been an important aid to man's work. Thus, the land tax created a chief supply of revenue all over the world. During the British rule in India, income from land continued to grow, and the motives for this were many. Early on, the British came to exchange with India. Slowly they tried to conquer the massive territory of India where they wanted all the money. In addition, they needed money for change, agency work, and a rate hike in management. The British overturned several land revenue checks, which accelerated the struggle for peasants. They extracted taxes from peasants to finance their policies and struggle efforts. Direct and indirect methods were employed to collect this revenue from the British. This affected the lives of those who could not meet their regular needs due to having to pay a percentage of their produce to landlords and collectors.

Key Words: Agrarian Relations, Changes in Agrarian Structure, Tenancy, Agricultural Laborers, Land Tenure Structure and Agricultural Growth

Introduction

Under British colonial rule, India's economy was essentially agricultural. About 85 percent of the population generally lived in villages, earning their livelihood either directly or indirectly from agriculture. However, despite the encroachment of this kind of large population, the rural area has experienced stagnation and is now occasionally experiencing extraordinary degradation. Although agricultural productivity remained low, in absolute terms, the sector saw some growth due to the expansion of the total area under cultivation. This stagnation in the farming sector was particularly accelerated by the many systems of land contracts added by the colonial government. Notably, under the zamindari machinery carried out within the then province of Bengal, which included parts of the present-day eastern states of India, profits in the agricultural sector went to the zamindars instead of the farmers. But a considerable number of zamindars and no longer the colonial government did nothing to improve the condition of agriculture. The primary interest of the zamindars was to collect wages irrespective of the economic status of the peasants. It forced titanic distress and social anxiety.¹ The phrasing of the revenue settlement was largely responsible for adopting such an attitude by the zamindars. Dates were fixed for depositing certain sale proceeds, failing which the zamindars would lose their rights. Apart from this, low levels of technology, loss of irrigation facilities, and careless use of fertilizers all worsened the plight of farmers and contributed to the poor level of agricultural production. Despite some progress in irrigation, India's agriculture became starved without investment in terracing, flood management, drainage, and soil desalination. Although a small proportion of farmers have shifted their cropping system from food crops to industrial crops, a large segment of tenants, small farmers, and sharecroppers lack the resources and generation, or motivation to invest in agriculture.

Agrarian Relations during British Rule in South India

The first half of the nineteenth century was a period of experimentation with methods of collecting land revenue. As the British extended their rule over South India, they were faced

¹ R. C. Majumdar, H. C. Raychaudhary, and K. Datta, *An Advanced History of India* (Madras: Macmillan India Limited, 1981), 794–6.

with the question of whom to settle with for the land revenue. Whether revenue is taken directly from individual cultivators or contracts is made with intermediaries. In general, the policy adopted was that, for the sake of political stability, there should be a minimum disturbance of traditional rights. However, the British did not always uphold this principle. Initially in certain districts ryotwari settlements were introduced. But soon after the introduction of Permanent Settlement in Bengal, similar arrangements were made in certain districts of the Madras Presidency. The land revenue was fixed in perpetuity, the zamindaris were made both inheritable and transferable, and uncultivated land was given to the zamindars tax-free.² The Zamindars were a diversified group. Some claimed descent from kings or military chieftains, others from tax officials. Yet others were new men who had bought estates. The zamindaris were varied in size. Some were enormous, sometimes covering almost the whole of a district while others consisted of just a few villages. Though the land revenue and tenure in this part of India was basically ryotwari, by 1830 over a third of the Presidency was under the zamindari system. Thereafter, the area under Zamindari declined. Whenever zamindars were unable to pay the revenue as demanded, the government confiscated their estates and converted them to ryotwari. But even then around one-fourth of the area remained under the zamindari system until the 1940s. In this part of India, the division of rights between the peasants and the zamindars remained undefined.³ It appears that the peasants of the southern zamindaris were in general more secure than those in the northern zamindaris. When the Permanent Settlement was introduced, it was assumed that the zamindars would collect half the gross produce and pay two-thirds of that to the government in cash, retaining one-third for the expenses of his revenue establishment and his personal income. But the actual collection from the peasants was much higher than this. For some time the land revenue collection from the villages in most areas was contracted out to middlemen, who might be former rent collectors, the leading cultivators of the village, or in some cases, speculators with little experience of the revenue system. These leases

² Dutt, The Economic History of India (New Delhi: Publication Division, Ministry of Information and Broadcasting, Government of India, 1960), vol. 1, 1–11, 127–75, 255–75, and vol. 2, pp. 22-70

³ Rayachaudhri, Tapan and Irfan Habib (Eds.), 1982, The Cambridge Economic History of India, Vol. 1, Cambridge University Press (Ch. IX), p.85

were initially to last for three or five years followed by decennial leases. But by 1822, it was decided that the ryotwari system should be introduced in all the non-zamindari areas, as and when the village leases expired. Under the ryotwari system, in principle, the land revenue was generally fixed at half the gross produce on un irrigated lands and three-fifths on irrigated lands. Besides the land revenue and the amounts officially set aside for community purposes and village officials, there was unrecorded plunder by revenue officials. The cultivator was thus often left with very little.

Changes in Agrarian Structure

During the latter half of the nineteenth century, the area under cultivation increased faster than the population. Large irrigation works were completed on the Godavari and the Krishna. The cultivation of cotton, groundnut, and oilseeds increased. The building of roads and railways facilitated trade. Between 1881-82 and 1915-16, the price of gains rose by 100 percent or even more. The terms of trade moved in favor of agriculture. ⁴The burden of land revenue fell. The cultivator was able to invest in land. Progress was rapid in some regions, notably the Krishna-Godavari delta. This led to a tremendous increase in the prices of land. In one village, Peddapadu in east Godavari, N.G. Ranga calculated in 1926 that the price of fertile land had risen from Rs. 40 to Rs. 1500 per acre in sixty years. The real income of the village had increased by 250 percent during the same period. The rich peasants widened the sphere of their activities and invested in rice mills, mica, and other industries. They extended their money lending business and went into banking. But the depression of the 1930s hit both the rich as well as the poor. Agricultural prices and employment fell sharply. Payment of fixed revenue became difficult. It was difficult for the farmers to pay back their loans. Grain looting and attacks on rich moneylenders and landlords were symptoms of widespread agrarian distress. The rural economy as a whole grew much poorer in the 1930s. Moreover, during the 20th century, the population was growing faster than the agricultural output. Until 1916 or so, the increase in agricultural output probably managed to match the increase in population; from then on the two diverged.

⁴ Balakrishnan P et al (2008) Agricultural Growth in India since 1991 Reserve Bank of India, Mumbai, pp167-169

Food grains output per head was 30 percent lower in 1946 than in 1916.⁵ The indebtedness of the rural population increased during the 19th century. The same trend continued during the early 20th century and during the Great Depression; the burden of debt became so pressing that the government was forced to take action. The debt conciliation boards set up by the government during the depression scaled-down debts in some cases but over the 1930s the volume of debt rose further. It was only during Second World War, when agricultural prices raised sharply, that, probably, there was a fall in the real burden of debt.

During British rule tenancy was grown slowly. The most common arrangement was sharecropping and the tenant commonly got half the crop on dry lands but his share could be less on fertile, irrigated lands ranging from one-third to one-fourth of the crop. The tenants' share also depended on input-sharing arrangements. Generally, the landlord paid the land revenue and made substantial repairs to the well and water channels. The tenant provided the manure. The quantities of manure per acre and the number of manuring were occasionally prescribed. Usually, the leases were oral but were continued for long periods. Tenants in ryotwari areas had no legal standing, and they bring a weak party, tenancy disputes were rare. Whether because of the relative infrequency of tenancy disputes or because of an implicit assumption that tenancy could not be a problem under a system of 'peasant proprietorship' like ryotwari, hardly any measures were taken in Madras presidency to protect tenants.

Agricultural Laborers

Indian rural society before British rule was composed of self-sufficient and independent village communities where agricultural products domestic industrial product and various services were directly exchanged between cultivators, artisans on the basis of an intra community combination of agriculture and handicraft. There every cultivator tilled his land with his family members. A separate class of agricultural laborers did not exist at all. When India was brought under the control of British rule and convened into a market for British industrial products, some village artisans lost their traditional occupation and became agricultural laborers.⁶

⁵ Ibid.,

⁶ Dr. J. Petal, agricultural laborers in modern India and Pakistan, 1952, pp.144-14

The lack of employment opportunities outside agriculture and the pressure of surplus population in the agricultural sector produced a class of semi-free laborers who sold their personal freedom and became bonded slaves. Many of them belonged to the depressed classes and tribal peoples. The proportion of the agricultural laborers to total agricultural working population widely varied from region to region. According to the 1931 census, the population was 58.8 per cent in south India (Bombay, Madras, central provinces, and Berar), 32.9 per cent in east India (Bihar, Orissa, Bengal, and Assam), and 19.9 per cent in north India (United Provinces, Punjab, and north-western frontier provinces). This regional difference was caused chiefly by the difference in land revenue systems, e.g., landownership systems. The transfer of land was easy and the disintegration of peasantry proceeded to a great extent in south India where the Raiyatwari land revenue system was prevalent and cultivators themselves were landowners.⁷

The incredible rise in the quantity of agricultural workers was the result of a huge social and economic renovation that went on in India during the nineteenth and twentieth centuries. A significant transform which took place during the nineteenth century was in the organization of village communities. The agrarian society of India, before British Rule, was founded on the integrated units of cultivation and handicrafts. Groups of cultivators and artisans, supplementing each other's needs, lived together in substantially self-sufficient village communities. The cultivators and the artisans lived together for centuries on the basis of traditional arrangements regulating the exchange of the cultivators' products and the artisans' services. Each cultivator carried on the cultivation of his farm with the assistance of his family. In such a society, there was no room for the existence of an independent and distinct class of agricultural laborers whose main source of livelihood was working on the land of others for which they received wages in kind or cash. During the 19th century, the village communities were confronted with economic, social and political changes of a far-reaching character, which served ultimately to bring about their disintegration. One of the reasons for their disintegration was the decline of domestic industries. With the Industrial Revolution in England, exports of British manufactured goods to India rose sharply. The construction of a network of railways during the latter half of the 19th century further stimulated it. The net result was a decline in handicrafts in India without being

⁷ Ibid.,

compensated by modern industrialization. Many artisans left their earlier professions and became agricultural laborers. As we have already noted earlier, with the introduction of the new land revenue system, private property in land was strengthened and free alienation of land was also granted. Further, under the new land revenue system, government revenue was a fixed amount, irrespective of crop output, and was to be paid in cash.⁸

Thus for the period of dreadful crops or low prices, the peasants were required to borrow from moneylenders to pay the land revenue. Once in the control of moneylenders, they were rarely able to free themselves from debt and the end result invariably was a mortgage or sale of land. This, in addition to commercialization, led to the proletarianisation of some deprived peasants and the attentiveness of land with a small number of resourceful rich peasants who later on employed the landless on their farms. Thus the decline of domestic industries and the disintegration of the peasantry led to the transformation of the social basis of the agrarian society in India. New classes appeared on the scene: the moneylenders and rich peasants on the one hand, pauperized peasants and agricultural laborers on the other.

Land Tenure Structure and Agricultural Growth

The consequence of all these changes in agrarian structure in India during the British period was the stagnation of the agricultural sector. During the period of 1891 to 1947 for British India as a whole, output rose at a rate of just 0.37 percent per annum. Besides, the increase rate of food grain productivity was 0.11 percent which was extensively lower than the population growth rate of 0.67 percent per annum. Agricultural crop output seems to have gradually increased over the period, but the pace was slower than population growth, especially after 1921⁹. Food grains output declined (after 1921) so per capita output fell markedly. Commercial crop output increased quickly, nearly doubling-up over the time.

⁸ Dutt, R.P., 1979, India Today, Manisha, Chs. IV and VIII Ghosh, Emergence of Capitalism in Indian Agriculture, P.P.H., New Delhi, p344

⁹ George Blyn, Trends in Agricultural Output in India, 1891-1947

Agricultural Output and Population Growth Rates in British India: 1891 to 1947

	Percentage growth rates (per annum) in			
	Food grains	Population	Non-food grains	All crops
British India	0.11	0.67	1.31	0.37
Greater Bengal	-0.73	0.65	0.23	-0.45
United Province	0.35	0.45	0.92	0.42
Madras	0.42	0.80	2.37	0.98
Punjab	1.10	0.93	2.40	1.57
Bombay and Sind	0.27	0.71	1.44	0.66
Central Provinces	0.29	0.58	0.07	0.48
Five Regions excluding Bengal	0.47	0.64		0.80

If we look at the regional trends, Greater Bengal's steep rate of decline stnon-food grains in this region, it is nullified by a significant decline in food grains output. The remaining regions all had growth rates higher than the British India average. But, only Punjab had average growth rate of food grains production higher than its population growth rate. In fact, its overall growth rate is also significantly higher than other states. In case of United Provinces the normal growth rate of food grains is roughly touching the population growth rate. The remaining three regions, however, had food grains growth rates considerably less than their population growth. Manufacture could have greater than before only through growth of area under manufacture or raising productivity. The potential for increasing yield per acre was great (considering its initial low level), but it appears that institutional as well as material requirements for growth were not conducive. Land tenurial structure was such that there were layers of intermediaries between the ultimate owner and actual cultivators. The owners of land in most cases were absentee landlords

without having any contact with land. The small cultivators, burdened by government taxes, heavy indebtedness, relatively high rent, and exploited by middlemen, did not have any margin to invest in land. It was not possible to invest by taking loans because of the high rate of interest and variable prices and yields.¹⁰

A substantial split of economic excess accrued to the landlords in the form of rents was being used up on prolific livelihood. To carry on their way of living many among them got greatly indebted. Stingy among the large owners mostly invested their money in the acquisition of land slightly than upgrading of agriculture. For moneylenders (agriculturists as well as professionals) money lending was more painful than any productive asset in land. As a result, net asset in agriculture was almost negligible and yield rates of most crops in different regions were either stagnant or declined. Increasing output of cash crops was mainly due to the shift of area from food grains to cash crops. Though in Punjab also, area under tenancy was quite high, but here generally tenants (who themselves were mostly small owners) leased in from landowners who were in general living in the village and supervising their cultivation. Tenancy in Punjab was basically a method of labour mobilization by those owners whose holdings were bigger (not as big as in zamindari areas) than what could be cultivated with family labour. Moreover, an important source of agricultural growth in Punjab was area expansion which increased during this period from 23 million acres to 31 million acres.¹¹

Though in India as an entire the British were neglecting irrigation works, yet in Punjab during this period there was a fabulous asset in irrigation. Area irrigated by government canals during 1901-02 to 1939-40 in Punjab increased from about 4.5 million acres to 12.5 million acres. In fact, irrigation was provided in those areas of Punjab which or else were deceitful empty due to insufficient rainfall; and with the stipulation of irrigation, area under agriculture also improved. In common, the productivity growth was higher in ryotwari and mahalwari areas. Greater Bengal

¹⁰ D. Naoroji. Poverty and British Rule in India (London: Swan Sonnenschein & Co, 1901), p.244

¹¹ Moreland, W.H., 1968, the Agrarian System of Moslem India, Oriental Books Reprint Corporation, Delhi. .p.58

was the area where land tenure formation was most retrogressive. There were layers of parasitic landowners living on rental incomes.¹² The traditional irrigation system kept decaying. Possibly these were the reasons for deterioration of agriculture there. In adding together, Bengal was the region where colonial exploitation was mainly voracious and lasted for the longest period. Punjab came under British rule much later when the burden of land revenue was relatively modest. The breakdown of handicrafts was also on a smaller level in the Punjab than in Bengal.

Conclusion

Traditional village economy undergoes social and economic transformation during the British rule, mainly through the turn down of handicrafts and household industries devoid of being remunerated by modern industries. This development resulted in formation of a whole lot of farming laborers. With the opening of new land revenue system, of course, right to disaffection of land was settled and land revenue was fixed at a exacting amount irrespective of intensity of production, but ghastly crops required the peasants to make use of from the money-lenders. Once fascinated in the control of money-lenders with scarcely any opportunity to liberate themselves from money owing, the peasants had no other opportunity but to funding or part with land. This, in adding together to commercialization of cultivation, led to the bankrupt of poor peasants and awareness of land in a small number of rich landlords. There were a few variations across regions in the nature of agrarian relation during the British period. On the other hand, the policies also led to improved pressure on land, overburdening of the farming sector, hardship of the peasantry, and the devastation of the self-sufficient rural community population. To this day these impacts continue to build India's farming sector

¹² Patel, Surendra J. 1952, Agricultural Labourers in Modern India and Pakistan, Current Book House, Bombay.p108

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